

A Possible Contradiction in Special Relativity Theory

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Abstract

It is a basic requirement of special relativity theory (SRT) that all relatively moving inertial observers agree on an observable (interference fringe shift, for example). It is shown that SRT leads to a disagreement on the observables (interference fringe shift) in two relatively moving inertial reference frames.

Introduction

It is a basic requirement of special relativity theory (SRT) that all relatively moving inertial observers agree on an observable (an interference fringe shift, for example) [1]. We show that SRT leads to a disagreement on the observables (interference fringe shift) in two relatively moving inertial reference frames.

Fringe shift predicted in two relatively moving inertial reference frames

Consider two inertial reference frames S and S', with origins O and O' respectively (see Fig.1). S' is moving with velocity v relative to S, in the $+x$ direction. S is the reference frame of the laboratory. At time $t = 0$, the origins O and O' coincide. An observer A with an interferometer is moving with velocity v_0 in the lab frame S, in the $+x$ direction and is just passing through the origin O at $t = 0$. To avoid the complications due to Doppler effect, we assume that the light source moves with velocity v_0 to the left, and is just passing through point E at $t = 0$.

The difference form of the Lorentz transformation equations is given below.

$$\Delta x' = \gamma (\Delta x - v \Delta t)$$

$$\Delta t' = \gamma \left(\Delta t - \frac{v \Delta x}{c^2} \right)$$

where

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$$

Δx is the difference in path lengths of the two light beams in frame S, and $\Delta x'$ is the difference in the path lengths of the two light beams in frame S'. Δt is the difference in the time of arrival of the two light beams in frame S, and $\Delta t'$ is the difference in time of arrival of the two light beams in frame S'.

Suppose that the interference fringe shift of the light speed experiment predicted in frame S is N , and the fringe shift predicted in frame S' for the same experiment is N' . It is a requirement of special relativity theory that there should be an agreement on the observable (the fringe shift) in both frames, i.e. $N = N'$. Let us see if this is actually the case.

We know that,

$$N = \frac{c \Delta t}{\lambda} \quad \text{and} \quad N' = \frac{c \Delta t'}{\lambda'}$$

or

$$N = \frac{\Delta x}{\lambda} \quad \text{and} \quad N' = \frac{\Delta x'}{\lambda'}$$

But, because of time dilation [1]:

$$\lambda' = \gamma \lambda$$

Therefore,

$$N' = \frac{c \Delta t'}{\lambda'} = \frac{c \gamma (\Delta t - \frac{v \Delta x}{c^2})}{\gamma \lambda} = \frac{c (\Delta t - \frac{v \Delta x}{c^2})}{\lambda} = \frac{c \Delta t}{\lambda} - \frac{v \Delta x}{\lambda} = N - \frac{v \Delta x}{c \lambda} \neq N$$

Galilean relativity, however, does not lead to such disagreement, as shown below.

$$\Delta x' = \Delta x - v \Delta t$$

$$\Delta t' = \Delta t$$

$$c' = c \pm V \Rightarrow \frac{c'}{c} = 1 \pm \frac{v}{c}$$

$$f' = f \Rightarrow \frac{c'}{\lambda'} = \frac{c}{\lambda} \Rightarrow \lambda' = \lambda (1 \pm \frac{v}{c})$$

Therefore,

$$N' = \frac{c' \Delta t'}{\lambda'} = \frac{(c \pm v) \Delta t}{\lambda(1 \pm \frac{v}{c})} = \frac{c \Delta t}{\lambda} = N$$

Consider the following hypothetical experiment for illustration.

In the lab frame S, the moving observer A detects the clockwise propagating light at (x_2, t_2) and the counter-clockwise propagating light at (x_3, t_3) .

Fig.1

In frame S, for the clockwise propagating light:

$$\frac{2l + h - x_2}{c} = \frac{x_2}{v_0}$$

$$\Rightarrow x_2 = \frac{v_0 (2l + h)}{c + v_0}$$

and

$$t_2 = \frac{x_2}{v_0} = \frac{(2l + h)}{c + v_0}$$

For the counter-clockwise propagating light:

$$\frac{2l + h + x_3}{c} = \frac{x_3}{v_0}$$

$$\Rightarrow x_3 = \frac{v_0 (2l + h)}{c - v_0}$$

and

$$t_3 = \frac{x_3}{v_0} = \frac{(2l + h)}{c - v_0}$$

$$\Delta x = x_3 - x_2 = v_0 (2l + h) \frac{2v_0}{c^2 - v^2}$$

$$\Delta t = t_3 - t_2 = (2l + h) \frac{2v_0}{c^2 - v^2}$$

The fringe shift as predicted in frame S can be written as:

$$N = \frac{\Delta x}{\lambda} = \frac{v_0 (2l + h) \frac{2v_0}{c^2 - v^2}}{\lambda}$$

But

$$\Delta x' = \gamma (\Delta x - v \Delta t)$$

$$\Rightarrow \Delta x' = \gamma \left(v_0 (2l + h) \frac{2v_0}{c^2 - v^2} - v (2l + h) \frac{2v_0}{c^2 - v^2} \right)$$

$$\Rightarrow \Delta x' = \gamma (2l + h) \frac{2v_0}{c^2 - v^2} (v_0 - v)$$

The fringe shift predicted in frame S' will be:

$$N' = \frac{\Delta x'}{\lambda'} = \frac{\gamma (2l + h) \frac{2v_0}{c^2 - v^2} (v_0 - v)}{\gamma \lambda} = \frac{(2l + h) \frac{2v_0}{c^2 - v^2} (v_0 - v)}{\lambda}$$

We already obtained,

$$N = \frac{\Delta x}{\lambda} = \frac{v_0 (2l + h) \frac{2v_0}{c^2 - v^2}}{\lambda}$$

Therefore,

$$N' = \left(1 - \frac{v}{v_0}\right) N$$

We can see that special relativity leads to a disagreement on the observed fringe shift in two inertial reference frames:

$$N' \neq N$$

For $v_0 = 0$, $N' = N = 0$. Therefore, the fringe shifts in S and S' agree only when $v_0 = 0$, that is when the observer looking at the fringe shifts is at rest relative to S. This is the case of the Michelson-Morley and similar experiments. In the case of $v_0 \neq 0$, which is the case of Sagnac effect and the hypothetical experiment discussed above, special relativity leads to a contradiction.

Conclusion

This paper has uncovered a flaw/ contradiction in special relativity theory that may have been overlooked for more than a century. We have seen that special relativity theory leads to a disagreement between inertial frames on observables (fringe shift). This contradiction is not present in the case of the Michelson-Morley and similar experiments, which is the reason it remained hidden for so long. A rigorous, consistent application of special relativity and Lorentz transformations, which has been lacking in many of the analyses made by physicists so far, has led to this finding. The prevailing practice has been an intuitive application of ad hoc mixture of length contraction, time dilation concepts (which are only consequences of the Lorentz transformations) and classical views.

Notes and references

1. Kennedy-Thorndike experiment, Wikipedia